

Heterocyclic Systems containing Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom. Synthesis of Thiadiazolo[2',3':2,1]imidazo[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline, Imidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles and their Brominated Products

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2-Amino-5-alkylthiadiazoles (1) condense with α -haloketones and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline to furnish respectively the cyclised products, 2,6-disubstituted imidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2) and 2-substituted-thiadiazolo[2',3':2,1]imidazo[4,5-*b*]-quinoxaline (4). Bromination of 2 furnishes 5-bromo-2,6-disubstituted-imidazo[2,1-*b*]-thiadiazoles (3). The antimicrobial activities of some of the compounds have been evaluated.

MIDAZOLE compounds possessing the grouping -N-C-N- display various biological activities¹, and have stimulated considerable interest to explore the possible synthesis of new biologically active² thiadiazole nucleus resulting in the synthesis of 2-alkyl-6-arylimidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles(2). Since the introduction of bromine atom into the thiazole ring³ augments considerably the antimicrobial properties of the system, bromination of 2 has been carried out to determine the effect of the introduction of bromine on the antimicrobial activities of imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiadiazoles.

Reaction of 2-aminothiadiazoles (1) (obtained by the condensation of aliphatic carboxylic acids with thiosemicarbazide in presence of concentrated H₂SO₄) with α -haloketones in anhydrous ethanol gave 2-alkyl-6-arylimidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2) which on bromination with bromine in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate yields 5-bromo-2,6-disubstituted-imidazo[2,1-*b*]thiadiazoles (3) as possible antibacterial and antifungal compounds. Similar condensation of 1 with 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline furnishes 2-substituted-thiadiazolo[2',3':2,1]-imidazo[4,5-*b*]quinoxaline (4), a novel and hitherto unknown heterocyclic system (Scheme 1).

The structures of 2-4 were established by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir and pmr spectra were recorded respectively on a Beckman IR-20 and a Perkin-Elmer R 32 (90 MHz) instruments (chemical shifts downfield from TMS).

2-Amino-5-*n*-hexyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1a): It was prepared⁴ from heptanoic acid and thiosemicarbazide in presence of concentrated H₂SO₄. Crystallisa-

Scheme 1. Reagent: (i) ArCOOH, Br, (ii) Br₂, NaOAc, (iii) 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline

tion from ethanol furnished 1a as light pink needles, (61%), m.p. 182° (Found: N, 23.18; S, 17.50. C₈H₁₄N₂S requires: N, 22.85; S, 17.39%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 500, 1 510, 1 630, 3 100 and 3 275 cm⁻¹.

Similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of 2-amino-5-*n*-heptyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1b) from *n*-octanoic acid and thiosemicarbazide, (42%), m.p. 186° (Found: N, 21.34; S, 15.80. C₉H₁₇N₂S requires: N, 21.10; S, 16.08%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 490, 1 510, 1 625, 3 100 and 3 275 cm⁻¹.

2-n-Hexyl-6-p-chlorophenylimidazo[2,1-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2a; Ar=p-Cl-C₆H₄): A mixture of **1a** (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide (2.34 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and neutralised with aqueous potassium carbonate solution. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as yellow coloured granular crystals (2.1 g, 69%), m.p. 112° (Found: N, 13.70; S, 10.25. C₁₆H₁₈N₂S requires: N, 13.15; S, 10.02%); $\nu_{\max}$ 710, 820, 1 515 and 1 640 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.63 (3H, t, CH₃), 0.75–1.30 (8H, m, CH₂(CH₂)₄CH₂), 2.92 (2H, t, CH₂(CH₂)₄CH₂), 7.49 (4H, q, *J* 8.1Hz, *p*-chlorophenyl protons) and 7.86 (1H, s, C₅-H).

A similar reaction on 2-amino-5-n-heptyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**1b**) and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide gave 2-n-heptyl-6-*p*-chlorophenylimidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**2b; Ar=p-Cl-C₆H₄; 54%**), m.p. 104° (Found: N, 12.87; S, 10.10. C₁₇H₂₀N₂S requires: N, 12.59; S, 9.60%); $\nu_{\max}$ 825, 1 520 and 1 640 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.87 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.31–1.91 (10H, m, CH₂(CH₂)₅CH₂), 2.94 (2H, t, CH₂(CH₂)₅CH₂), 7.49 (4H, q, *J* 8.1Hz, *p*-chlorophenyl protons), 7.86 (1H, s, C₅-H).

Other imidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**2**) prepared similarly were: **2a** (Ar=C₆H₅), (62%), m.p. 100° (Found: N, 14.98; S, 11.67. C₁₅H₁₆N₂S requires: N, 14.74; S, 11.23%); $\nu_{\max}$ 705, 735, 1 590 and 1 635 cm⁻¹; **2a** (Ar=*p*-Br-C₆H₄), (65%), m.p. 111° (Found: N, 11.84; S, 9.22. C₁₆H₁₆N₂SBr requires: N, 11.54; S, 8.79%); $\nu_{\max}$ 820, 1 525 and 1 640 cm⁻¹; **2a** (Ar=*p*-C₆H₅-C₆H₄), (66%), m.p. 130° (Found: N, 12.08; S, 9.28. C₂₂H₂₂N₂S requires: N, 11.68; S, 8.86%); $\nu_{\max}$ 720, 755, 835, 1 480 and 1 600 cm⁻¹; **2b** (Ar=C₆H₅), (60%), m.p. 220° (Found: N, 14.26; S, 11.12. C₁₇H₂₁N₂S requires: N, 14.05; S, 10.70%); $\nu_{\max}$ 720, 745, 1 500, 1 570 and 1 640 cm⁻¹; **2b** (Ar=*p*-Br-C₆H₄), (42%), m.p. 116° (Found: N, 11.49; S, 8.14. C₁₇H₂₀N₂SBr requires: N, 11.11; S, 8.47%); $\nu_{\max}$ 820, 1 500 and 1 640 cm⁻¹; **2b** (Ar=*p*-C₆H₅-C₆H₄), (53%), m.p. 120° (Found: N, 11.62; S, 8.90. C₂₃H₂₅N₂S requires: N, 11.20; S, 8.53%); $\nu_{\max}$ 715, 735, 800, 850, 1 510, 1 590 and 1 630 cm⁻¹.

5-Bromo-2-n-heptyl-6-p-chlorophenylimidazo[2,1-*b*]-1,3,4-thiadiazole (3; Ar=p-Cl-C₆H₄): Bromine (0.50 g, 0.0066 mol) was added dropwise to a well-stirred mixture of **2b** (Ar=*p*-Cl-C₆H₄; 1.00 g, 0.003 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.50 g, 0.006 mol) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) and the stirring continued for further 10 min. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water and kept overnight. The yellow solid thus separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as light pink flakes (1 g, 72%), m.p. 86° (Found: N, 9.87; S, 7.21. C₁₇H₁₉N₂BrClS requires: N, 10.18; S, 7.76%); $\nu_{\max}$ 710, 825, 1 510, 1 560 and 1 590 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.88 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.12–2.02 (10H, m, CH₂(CH₂)₅CH₂), 3.01 (2H, t,

CH₂(CH₂)₅CH₂) and 7.67 (4H, q, *J* 8.1Hz, *p*-chlorophenyl protons).

2-n-Hexylthiadiazolo[2',3':2,1]imidazo[4,5-*b*]-quinoxaline (4): A mixture of **1a** (0.92 g, 0.005 mol), 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (1.0 g, 0.005 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) in dry ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and poured into ice-water. The resulting yellow solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as orange coloured flakes (0.8 g, 51%), m.p. 175° (Found: N, 22.91, S, 10.64. C₁₆H₁₇N₅S requires: N, 22.51; S, 10.29%); $\nu_{\max}$ 710, 750, 1 475, 1 500 and 1 620 cm⁻¹.

Antimicrobial activities: **2a** (Ar=*p*-Br-C₆H₄), **2b** (Ar=*p*-Cl-C₆H₄), **3b** (Ar=*p*-Cl-C₆H₄) and **4** were studied for their antibacterial activity against gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and for their antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* using neat samples and serial plate dilution method⁵.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of the compounds **3b** against *C. albicans* was found to be 500 μ g cm⁻³. **2a** (Ar=*p*-Br-C₆H₄) and **2b** (Ar=*p*-Cl-C₆H₄) showed activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *Ps. aeruginosa* when tested as neat sample whereas **4** showed the neat activity only against *Ps. aeruginosa*. The samples showing neat activity may be used for local application in the form of powder or ointment provided further studies indicate the absence of toxicity.

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